

A spectroscopic study of the composition and conformation of cholesteryl and wax esters purified from meibum

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ABSTRACT

Elucidating wax ester (WE) and cholesteryl ester (CE) compositional, structural and functional relationships is key to our understanding of how these lipids are involved in natural and pathological processes. Little is known about how CE and WE interact with one another. The focus of the present study is to bridge this gap of knowledge. CE and WE were collected from human meibum as a source of esters with complex hydrocarbon chains. MgO column chromatography was used to separate WE and CE. The esters were characterized using ¹H-NMR and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The complexity of the hydrocarbon chains of native WE and CE influenced how changes in the ratio of WE and CE ester influenced some lipid phase transitional parameters but not others. Changes in CE content of WE/CE mixtures undoubtedly modifies the hydrocarbon chain conformation and packing of the mixture. The nature of the change depends on the conformation of the WE and CE. Differences in the complexity of the hydrocarbon chains are likely not to be a major influence on alterations in the order or phase transition temperature when more ordered WE is added to less ordered CE.

1. Introduction

Wax ester (WE) (Fig. 1a) and cholesteryl ester (CE) (Fig. 1b) are found in: sebum, on the surface of skin (Mudgil et al., 2016; Robosky et al., 2008); meibum (Borchman et al., 2019; Nicolaides et al., 1981), a major source of tear lipids; the cuticle of plants (Dyas and Goad, 1992; Turkish and Sturley, 2009); the spermaceti of whales (Koopman, 2018), and the exoskeleton coating of insects (Sharma et al., 2018). Little is known about how CE and WE interact with one another. The focus of the present study is to bridge this gap of knowledge. CE became widely studied after a seminal publication (Katz, 1981) showed that CE contributes to plaque formation in human aortic intima, contributing to atherosclerosis (Small and Shipley, 1974; Small, 1988). In humans, CE transports cholesterol to specific organs (Brown et al., 1980; Franceschini et al., 1991), a process that could be important to ocular lens clarity as cholesterol levels are extremely high in the human lens, and

ocular cholesterol levels are related to lifespan and cataract formation (Borchman and Yappert, 2010; Borchman et al., 2017; Stimmelmayer and Borchman, 2018). Sebum contains higher amounts of CE in patients with sensitive scalp compared with those without the condition (Ma et al., 2019).

WE serves many functions. For some desert insects, WE on their exoskeleton reflects sun light and prevents water loss (Cerkowniak et al., 2013). Plants are protected from transpiration, pathogens and ultraviolet radiation by epicuticular wax (Sharma et al., 2018). Wax in the human ear protects the eardrum from debris (Okuda et al., 1991). In many marine species, WE is a storage depot for lipids, plays a role in the reception and transmission of sound, and provides buoyancy (Koopman, 2018).

Maintenance of the ratio of CE/WE in human tear lipids may be important to tear film stability and the prevention of dry eye. CE and WE make up ~ 80 % of human meibum (Borchman et al., 2019; Butovich

Abbreviations: WEo, Wax ester enriched from human meibum from an older donor; CEo, Cholesteryl ester enriched from human meibum from an older donor; WEy, Wax ester enriched from human meibum from a younger donor; CEy, Cholesteryl ester enriched from human meibum from a younger donor; CE, cholesteryl ester; FTIR, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy; $\bar{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$, The frequency of the symmetric CH₂ stretching band near 2850 cm⁻¹; Tc, The phase transition temperature; WE, Wax ester.

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et al., 2008; Green-Church et al., 2011; Lam et al., 2011; Shine and McCulley 1991; Shrestha et al., 2011), the major source of tear lipids (Borchman et al., 2013a; Murube, 2012; Mudgil et al., 2016). Two populations of donors have been observed, with lower and higher ratios of CE/WE (Borchman et al., 2019; Shine and McCulley, 1991; Shrestha et al., 2011). The CE/WE ratio has been shown to decrease in patients with meibomian gland dysfunction (Borchman et al., 2019) and increase between birth and 19 years of age (Borchman et al., 2019; Shrestha et al., 2011). It is unclear whether changes in CE/WE ratio are related to tear film stability or are markers for, and/or contributes to dry eye disease. Nor is it known how native CE influences the structure of meibum.

The key to understanding how CE and WE are involved in natural and pathological processes is to elucidate the compositional, structural and functional relationships of these lipids. Vibrational spectroscopy has been a valuable tool to measure lipid hydrocarbon chain conformation (structure). For instance, a seminal study showed that cholesterol increases the phase transition temperature and broadness of phospholipid phase transitions, increases the order of disordered hydrocarbon chains, and decreases the order of ordered hydrocarbon chains (Lippert and Peticolis, 1971). The relationships among lens membrane cholesterol content, membrane lipid conformation, and cataract have been reviewed (Borchman, 2021; Borchman et al., 1996; Borchman and Yappert, 2010). The variable hydrocarbon chains found in CE and WE adds a layer of complexity to the relationships between CE and WE interactions that cholesterol does not have. Vibrational spectroscopy has also been used to study straight chain hydrocarbon WE and CE interactions (Borchman et al., 2013b; Hetman and Borchman, 2020). Like cholesterol, CE dramatically increased the phase transition temperature of pure WE. However, unlike cholesterol, CE increased the order of ordered WE, indicating that the acyl chain of CE impacts WE hydrocarbon chain order.

In the current study, we used infrared spectroscopy to analyze native WE and CE fractions from meibum to determine if or how CE influences WE hydrocarbon chain conformation and vice-versa. Human meibum was used as a source of CE and WE because meibum is mostly composed of CE and WE, 80 %, and the esters contain complex hydrocarbon chains (Butovich, 2009, 2010; Butovich et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2010, 2013; Chen and Nichols, 2018; Nicholades et al., 1981; 35–41). The current study adds a layer of complexity to previous cholesterol, CE and WE studies, as native CE and WE acyl chains have variable lengths, saturation and branching whereas cholesterol and model synthetic CE and WE do not.

The three major aims of the study were to answer the following questions:

- 1 Could human meibum WE and CE be completely separated?
- 2 Does the complexity of the hydrocarbon chains found in human meibum WE and CE influence how changes in the ratio of WE and CE ester influence hydrocarbon chain conformation?
- 3 Why is WE and CE often present together and how does WE influence CE hydrocarbon chain conformation and visa-versa.

To answer question one, we used adsorption column chromatography with a MgO solid phase to separate CE from WE from human meibum. To answer questions two and three, we compared the phase transitions of meibum WE and CE mixtures that have complex hydrocarbon chains, to those of simpler synthetic WE and CE from previous studies. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy was used to characterize the separated CE and WE, and from infrared spectra, lipid structure and conformation were determined similar to previous studies (Borchman, 2021).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and standards

HPLC-grade hexane, chloroform and D -chloroform (CDCl_3) were acquired from Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis MO.

2.2. Meibum collection

Written consents were obtained from the two volunteers, and all protocols were in accordance with the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. Protocols and procedures for the current retrospective study were approved by the University of Louisville Institutional Review Board (# 11.0319, August 2016). The donors did not complain of dry eye disease and their meibomian gland orifices showed no evidence of keratinization or plugging with turbid or thickened secretions, and no dilated blood vessels were observed on the eyelid margin. Meibum collection was done by medically qualified personnel. Meibum was expressed from four eye lids of each volunteer using an ILUX instrument (Alcon, Fort Worth, TX) (Tauber et al., 2020) according to the manufacturer's instructions after a mild anesthesia with proparacaine hydrochloride ophthalmic, 0.5 % drops (Bausch and Lomb, Bridgewater, NJ) was introduced in each eye. The ILUX instrument delicately clamps on each eye lid, warming them for ~ 90 s, and then applies gentle pressure on the eye lid to express the visible meibum magnified by ILUX. Approximately 0.5 mg of meibum lipid was obtained at each collection per donor. Meibum from two donors, was collected five times over a period of a month. The meibum from each donor was separately pooled. Each expressate was collected with a platinum spatula and immediately dissolved into 0.5 mL of CDCl_3 in a 9-mm glass microvial with a Teflon cap (Microliter Analytical Supplies Ind., Suwanee, GA). Samples were stored in the freezer until their use in separation. The samples were never exposed to any plastic to avoid plasticizers. Control CDCl_3 spectra were run with the meibum samples to ensure no impurities were present in the CDCl_3 .

2.3. Column chromatographic separation of CE and WE from human meibum

A glass column of 1.7 cm inside diameter and 43.5 cm length (excluding cotton wool sitting) was made. A slurry of MgO and chloroform was used to make the MgO stationary phase. The solution of the pooled meibum (1 mL) was layered onto the column. Separation of CE

Fig. 1. a) The structure of the wax ester oleyl oleate. The arrow show protons that were used to quantify wax esters at 4.0 ppm using $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy. b) The structure of a cholesteryl ester where R is a hydrocarbon chain. The proton on carbon #3 at 4.6 ppm was used to quantify cholesteryl esters using $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy. The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ resonance assignments were made for the protons on the numbered carbons.

and WE was achieved with a 13.1 cm column slurry height and varying elution solvent volume for both donors. Consecutive 25 mL aliquots of 250 mL hexane initiated the younger donor meibum lipids' separation gradient course with 37 percolated fractions for ~ 3.25 h, and then added aliquots of 100 % chloroform were used, yielding 26 eluate portions for ~1.75 h. The final forty fractions, including those suspected to contain unseparated CEy and WEy, were ran twice again by gradient elution. For the older donor meibum lipids' separation, 25 mL aliquots of 175 mL hexane were added in the beginning, and then 25 mL aliquots of binary eluent mixtures of 95:5, 93:7, 90:10, 85:15, 70:30, 50:50, 0:100 hexane: chloroform (vol: vol) were introduced sequentially. Fractions were collected in a beaker each hour for the first 120 min, with subsequent collections in 27 test tubes for 73 min, followed by a 77-minute final collection in a beaker. All fractions were left in ambient conditions for 5 days in a fume hood to evaporate solvent(s). CE and WE separated from the older donor are abbreviated CEo and WEo. CE and WE separated from the younger donor are abbreviated CEy and WEy.

2.4. Combining CE and WE

The four samples in 600 μL of CDCl_3 , CEo, WEo, CEy and WEy, were mixed proportionally to give a range of CE/WE ratios as in Table 1. A X axis value of 20 % in the figures (20 % CE (% total esters separated)) was obtained by mixing 20 μL of CEo with 80 μL of WEo, or by mixing 20 μL CEy with 80 μL WEy. After mixing the WE with the CE, 500 μL of CDCl_3 was added to each sample as listed in Table 1. Since we were interested only in the molar ratio of WE and CE, we did not calculate the concentrations of purified WE and CE which we estimate to be around 1 mg each. The molar ratio of CE / WE was measured using NMR spectroscopy (Borchman et al., 2019a). CE has a characteristic resonance at 0.66 ppm and 1.01 ppm, while WE has a resonance at 4.0 ppm (multiple citations in Borchman and Ramasubramanian, 2019). Areas under these NMR resonances were quantified, and the molar CE/WE ratio calculated, factoring in the hydrogen resonance contribution by each type of ester (Borchman et al., 2019b).

2.5. NMR spectroscopy

A 700 MHz ^1H -NMR was used to analyze every collected fraction. Each of the fractions were reconstituted with 600 μL D-chloroform and analyses were performed with 250 scans, 45° pulse width, a 1.000 s relaxation delay between 0–11 ppm. Pooled CE and WE samples from both donors, as well as a blank of chloroform, were measured using the same conditions but with 1024 scans. Chemical-shifts were referenced to the CDCl_3 resonance at 7.25 ppm resonance.

GRAMS/386 software (Galactic Industries, Salem, NH) was used to

Table 1
Standard Curves for the calculation of the mole % CE.

YX axis tick label Figs. 3, 4 and 5	Purified WE in CDCl_3 (μL)	Purified CE in CDCl_3 (μL)	CDCl_3 (μL)	CE (mole %)
Meibum from older donor				
0	100	0	500	0
20	80	20	500	12.0
30	70	30	500	15.7
40	60	40	500	22.2
50	50	50	500	28.9
75	25	75	500	37.0
100	0	100	500	100
Meibum from younger donor				
0	100	0	500	0
20	80	20	500	7.6
30	70	30	500	9.0
40	60	40	500	10.8
50	50	50	500	14.0
75	25	75	500	25.0
100	0	100	500	100

analyze all spectra. Hydrocarbon chain branching (Borchman and Ramasubramanian, 2019), saturation (Mudgil et al., 2013; Nencheva et al., 2018; Sledge et al., 2017) and the molar ratios of CE to WE (Borchman et al., 2019; Shrestha et al., 2011) were calculated as described previously.

2.6. Measurement of lipid phase transitions using FTIR spectroscopy

Purified CE and WE each in a total volume of 0.6 mL CDCl_3 were mixed as shown in Table 1. Lipid phase transitions were measured as described previously (Borchman et al., 2007). "All of the 600 μL of sample in CDCl_3 was applied to a KCl infrared window. The solvent was evaporated under a stream of Argon gas and the window was placed in a lyophilizer for 4 h to remove all traces of solvent. Infrared spectra were measured using a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (Nicolet 5000 Magna Series; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc., Waltham MA). Lipid on the KCl window was placed in a temperature-controlled infrared cell. The cell was jacketed by an insulated water coil connected to a circulating water bath (model R-134A; Neslab Instruments, Newton NH). The sample temperature was measured and controlled by a thermistor touching the sample cell window. The water bath unit was programmed to measure the temperature at the thermistor and to adjust the bath temperature so that the sample temperature could be set to the desired value. The rate of heating or cooling (1 $^\circ\text{C}/15$ min) at the sample was also adjusted by the water bath unit. Temperatures were maintained within ± 0.01 $^\circ\text{C}$. Exactly 100 interferograms were recorded and averaged. Spectral resolution was set to 1.0 cm^{-1} . Infrared data analysis was then performed (GRAMS/386 software; Galactic Industries, Salem, NH). The frequency of the symmetric CH_2 stretching band near 2850 cm^{-1} ($\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$) was used to estimate the content of *trans* and *gauche* rotamers in the hydrocarbon chains. $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ was calculated by first baseline leveling the OH—CH stretching region between 3500 and 2700 cm^{-1} . The wavenumber (cm^{-1}) associated with an infrared band has been historically called the frequency of the band since it is proportional and related to vibronic frequencies (Casal et al., 1980; Kóta et al., 1999; Moore and Mendelsohn, 1994). The center of mass of the CH symmetric stretching band was calculated by integrating the top 10 % of the intensity of the band. The baseline for integrating the top 10 % of the intensity of the band was parallel to the OH—CH region baseline. The change in $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ versus temperature was used to characterize lipid phase transitions as described previously (Borchman et al., 2007). Since rotamers are either in *trans* or *gauche* conformations, phase transitions were fit to a two-state sigmoidal equation using Sigma plot 10 software (Systat Software, Inc. Chicago IL):

Equation 1:

$$\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}} = (\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}})_{\text{minimum}} + ((\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}})_{\text{maximum}} - (\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}})_{\text{minimum}}) / (1 + (\text{temperature}/\text{Tc})^{\text{hillslope}})$$

$\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ is the frequency of the symmetric CH_2 stretching band near 2850 cm^{-1} . Tc is the phase transition temperature.

Lipid order at 33.4 $^\circ\text{C}$ was calculated by extrapolating the $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ at 33.4 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 36 $^\circ\text{C}$ from the fit of the phase transition and then converting $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ to the percentage of *trans* rotamers, a measure of lipid conformational order. The data for percentage of *trans* rotamer were used to calculate the phase-transition enthalpy and entropy from the slopes of Arrhenius plots."

2.7. Lipid phase transitions

In the current study, temperature was used to cause meibum lipid to go from an ordered phase to a disordered phase. From the phase transitions, we can measure the strength of lipid-lipid interactions, and the order of lipids at the temperature of the meibomian glands at 36 $^\circ\text{C}$ and on the surface of the eye, 33.4 $^\circ\text{C}$ (Abreau et al., 2016). Lipid order may be an important parameter to measure as it is related to tear film

stability (Borchman, 2021; Georgiev et al., 2017). As described previously (Borchman, 2021), “Hydrocarbon chain conformation may be used to measure hydrocarbon structural order, a static measure of lipid fluidity. Conformation is the spatial arrangement of atoms in a molecule that can come about through the rotation of the atoms about a chemical bond. When lipids are completely ordered, the CH₂ moieties are arranged in an all *trans* conformation of rotamers (Fig. 2). This allows the lipid hydrocarbon chains to pack tightly together maximizing van der Waal’s interactions between chains. When the hydrocarbon chains are disordered, the number of CH₂ *gauche* rotamers increases, the lipids pack more loosely, and van der Waal’s interactions are minimal (Fig. 2).

Meibum exists in a liquid crystalline phase at lower temperatures. The term ‘liquid crystalline phase’ is used because meibum never is a solid with 100 % *trans* as the meibum hydrocarbon chains contain about 72 % *trans* rotamers, allowing them to pack tightly together (Fig. 2) (Borchman, 2021). Consequently, the term ‘liquid crystalline’ phase is used rather than ‘solid phase’. At higher temperatures, meibum is in the gel phase and the conformation of the meibum lipid hydrocarbon chains is about 18 % *trans* rotamers and 82 % *gauche* rotamers (Fig. 2). Therefore, meibum is not a liquid (0 % *trans*) but rather in the ‘gel phase.’ Eight parameters can be measured from phase transitional data obtained from infrared spectra. They have been defined previously (Mudgil et al., 2013; Sledge et al., 2017).

3. Results

3.1. Enrichment/purification of CE and WE

CE and WE were separated from meibum donated by two healthy volunteers who did not show signs of dry eye or Meibomian gland occlusion. One donor, was a 66-year-old Caucasian male and the other donor, was a 29-year-old black male. Race has no statistically significant influence on the composition of meibomian samples when the donors were matched by age (Alghamdi et al., 2016; Butovich et al., 2020). WE began to elute with 100 % hexane for both donors, after 20 min into the run. CEo began to elute 2.5 h with hexane: chloroform mixture while CEy began to elute after 3.5 h. A few fractions from the younger donor in which CE and WE were not completely separated, were run a second time by gradient elution. Fractions were initially analyzed using ¹H-NMR to determine which fractions contained WE or CE (Fig. 3). Fractions with WE or CE were each pooled and analyzed more carefully (Fig. 4). ¹H-NMR spectra of CE and WE enriched from meibum are

Fig. 2. A typical lipid phase transition of a meibum mixture of wax ester and cholesteryl ester from the younger donor containing 7.6 mol % cholesteryl ester. The larger the Y axis value the more disordered the hydrocarbon chains. Insets show the conformation of ordered hydrocarbon chains containing all *trans* rotamers and disordered *gauche* rotamers.

Fig. 3. A) and B) ¹H-NMR spectra of fractions from MgO column. a) human meibum from the older donor prior to loading on the column. b) Wax ester fraction 1 c) Wax ester fraction 2. d) Cholesteryl ester fraction 20. e) Cholesteryl ester fraction 22. Similar fractions to 1 and 2, 20 and 22 were pooled and analyzed more carefully. See Fig. 4 and Table 2 for resonance assignments.

presented in Fig. 4. Resonance assignments are presented in Table 2. Note that resonances assigned to CE (Table 2), numbers 1 and 3 in Fig. 4A and numbers 6, 7, 8 and 18 in Fig. 4B, are missing in the WE spectra (Fig. 4a and b) and present in the CE spectra (Fig. 4c and d), indicating that the WE was completely separated from the CE. From the intensity of the ester resonance number 5 (Fig. 4A c and d) relative to the resonances numbered 3, 6, 7, 8, 18 in Fig. 4, we calculate (Borchman et al., 2019a) that the molar ratio of CEo/WEo and CEy/WEy was 2.4 and 1.4, respectively. Compared to the average molar ratio of CE/WE for individuals without dry eye of 0.49 (Borchman et al., 2019a) CEo and CEy was enriched 3 and 5 fold, respectively. CE may even have been completely separated from WE considering 7 % of the resonance # 5 intensity in the spectra of purified CE is likely to be due to cholesteryl diesters (ω Type 1-SE) (Chen et al., 2013) and not due to unseparated WE.

3.2. Hydrocarbon chain branching

Hydrocarbon chain branching is shown in Table 3. The branching for the younger donor was comparable for CE and WE. The hydrocarbon chain branching for WEo compared with WEy were similar and within the range of previous studies (Butovich et al., 2016; Nicolaidis et al., 1981) (Table 3). The hydrocarbons of CEo contained more much less anteiso and more straight chains compared with CEy. Whether this difference is within the level of normal variation is not known as branching in CE has not been measured in other studies. WEo had 16 % less straight-chains and 50 % more iso-chains compared with CEo.

Fig. 4. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of (a and b) wax ester and (c and d) cholesteryl ester separated from meibum. A) The = CH and ester region of the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra. B) the CH_3 region of the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra. (a and c) Meibum from the older donor. (b and d) Meibum from the younger donor. Resonance numbering in (A) and (B) refer to resonance assignments in Fig. 1, and Table 2.

Table 2

Assignments for resonances numbered in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 resonance #	Chemical- Shift (ppm)	Proton Resonance Assignment. The carbon # refers to the protons on that carbon (Fig. 1b).
1	5.36	Cholesterol Carbon #6
2	5.33	Hydrocarbon = CH- <i>cis</i>
3	4.6	Cholesteryl Ester Carbon #3
4	3.9	Wax Ester $-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-(\text{C}=\text{O})-$
5	3.9	Cholesteryl di ester $-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-(\text{C}=\text{O})-$
6	0.998	Cholesterol Carbon # 19
7	0.906	Cholesterol Carbon #21
8	0.897	Cholesterol Carbon #21
9	0.878	Straight-chain
9	0.868	Straight-chain
11	0.858	Straight-chain
12	0.853	Iso-branched
13	0.850	Anteiso-branched
14	0.843	Iso-branched
15	0.839	Anteiso-branched
16	0.829	Anteiso-branched
17	0.821	Anteiso-branched
18	0.663	Cholesterol Carbon #18

3.3. Phase transitional parameters

FTIR phase transition data (Figs. 5 and 6) were plotted against the % total CE separated relative to the % total WE separated, based on volume according to Table 1. For example, a value of 20 % in Table 1 represents 20 μL of the total amount of CE separated mixed with 80 μL of the total amount of WE separated. To convert the volume % values in Table 1 to mole % CE, the intensity of resonances at 4, 1 and 0.65 ppm were used as described previously (Borchman et al., 2019). The standard curves were linear, $r = 0.992$, 0.985 and slopes of 0.528 and 0.311 were calculated for Fig. 7A and B, respectively.

All of the phase transition parameters for the WEy and CEy were higher, $P < 0.05$, compared with WEo and CEo (Table 4) indicating that

Table 3

Hydrocarbon chain branching.

	Anteiso Branched (%)	Straight Chain (%)	Iso Branched (%)	Branched (%)
Wax Esters				
Older donor	8	74	18	26
Younger donor	18	79	3	21
Average	13	76	11	24
Citation (Butovich et al., 2016)	11	83	5	16
Citation (Nicolaides et al., 1981)	13	78	9	22
Cholesteryl Esters and di Esters				
Older donor	3	88	9	12
Younger donor	15	79	6	21

WEy and CEy was more ordered compared with the same samples from donor A. The phase transition temperature, order, and maximum frequency of the phase transition of CEo were lower compared with the WEo (Table 4) indicating CEo was more fluid compared with WEo. Conversely, and serendipitously, the phase transition temperature, order, and maximum frequency of the phase transition of CEy was higher compared with the WEy (Table 4). So, by mixing the WE and CE esters from each sample, we could determine how the structure of a WE that was more ordered (stiffer) was influenced by a less ordered CE and vice versa.

Adding 25 % more ordered WEo (compared with CEo) to CEo, significantly, $P < 0.05$, decreased the hydrocarbon chain order and phase transition temperature (Fig. 5, Table 5). These changes indicate that addition of 25 % WEo to CEo caused a structural rearrangement of molecules leading to a more disordered system. At higher temperatures, when the lipids are maximally disordered, adding 25 % WEo to CEo increased the maximum frequency from $2853.6 \pm 0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $2854.25 \pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 5), indicating that when WEo is added to CEo, the resulting mixture becomes even more disordered. Increasing amounts of less ordered CEo (compared with WEo) added to more ordered WEo caused the hydrocarbon chain order and phase transition temperature to decrease linearly, excluding 100 % CEo (Fig. 5, Table 6). It is interesting that when the lipids are at low temperatures and maximally ordered, adding less ordered CEo to more ordered WEo causes the minimum frequency to decrease linearly, indicating that the mixture becomes even more ordered with the addition of CEo.

Adding 25 % less ordered WEy (compared with CEy) to CEy, significantly, $P < 0.05$, decreased the hydrocarbon chain order and phase transition temperature similar to adding WEo to CEo above (Fig. 6, Table 5). These changes indicate that like the addition of WEo to CEo, the addition of 25 % WEy to CEy caused a structural rearrangement of molecules leading to a less ordered system. At higher temperatures, when the lipids are maximally disordered, adding 25 % WEo to CEo decreased the maximum frequency slightly but significantly from $2854.34 \pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $2854.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 5), indicating that when WEo is added to CEo, the resulting mixture becomes slightly more ordered.

CEy added to less ordered WEy (compared with CEy) caused the hydrocarbon chain order and phase transition temperature to increase linearly above 20 % CEy, while causing a linear decrease in the ΔS and ΔH (Fig. 6, Table 6).

4. Discussion

4.1. Enrichment of WE and CE from human meibum

The answer to the question addressed in aim 1 is yes: WE and CE could be completely separated. Greater separation of CE from WE could always be made if necessary, by a second passage of select fractions. We

Fig. 5. Phase transition parameters for meibum from older donor. X axis data are from mixtures listed in Table 1, where a value of 20 % represents 20 μ L of the total amount of CE separated mixed with 80 μ L of the total amount of WE separated. The molar ratio of CE/WE is listed in Table 1. Phase transition parameters measured: A) Phase transition temperature, B) Lipid order at 33.4 °C, the temperature of the tear film surface, C) Lipid order at 36 °C, the temperature of the meibomian glands, D) Minimum frequency.

used a slurry of MgO and chloroform to prepare a column for the separation of human meibum WE and CE based on previous studies that used a slurry of MgO and water to make thin layer chromatography plates (Kaufmann et al., 1971; Nicolaides, 1970). Our study was unique because we used column chromatography rather than thin layer chromatography. A seminal study of human meibum used this separation technique (Nicolaides et al., 1981). The mixing of MgO with water chemically yields MgOH. Hence, another tenable optimization approach may be to use MgOH instead of MgO, which creates a less porous slurry, possibly facilitating better separation. Like MgO, thin layer chromatography plates of MgOH efficiently separate WE and CE (Stewart and Downing, 1981). Urea adducts of CE and WE improved the separation of CE and WE for rabbit meibum, but could not be used in this study because the adduct could change the physical properties of the esters (Tiffany and Marsden, 1982). Other oxides and/or hydroxides, besides MgO or MgOH have yet to be explored for the separation of CE and WE. We used a 13 cm high column slurry length which efficiently separated CE and WE, but it is conceivable that using a shorter column may reduce total chromatography time whilst achieving same separation resolution. The significant disparity between the elution times of CE₀ and CE_Y was most likely influenced by solvents composition, as more hexane, which is a slower eluent compared to chloroform, was used for our separation of younger donor meibum esters compared to the older donor. This allowed enough time for lipid – stationary phase interactions,

facilitating better separation, before introducing 100 % chloroform. The latter separation of older donor meibum esters involved a more fine-tuned protocol facilitated by more solvent gradient, leading to a faster and smoother separation. Gradient elution therefore, gave the optimum separation. ¹H-NMR which was used to detect CE and WE in the current study is advantageous over rhodamine 6 G, and UV visualization used previously (Kaufmann et al., 1971; Nicolaides et al., 1981) as NMR spectroscopy does not alter the sample whereas rhodamine could.

4.2. Question addressed in aim 2. Does the complexity of the hydrocarbon chains found in human meibum WE and CE influence how changes in the ratio of WE and CE ester influence hydrocarbon chain conformation?

Changes in the conformation and phase characteristics of CE and WE lipid structure may be grouped into three categories: i) the change when pure smectic CE (Fig. 8f) is mixed with WE; ii) When pure lamellar WE (Fig. 8e) is mixed with CE and iii) when the concentration of CE is varied in a mixture of WE and CE (Fig. 8g). In each category, we considered the situations when CE is more ordered or less ordered than WE.

The major finding of the current study is that enriched native CE can influence the conformation of native enriched WE depending on whether the CE is more ordered or less ordered than WE. Many of the infrared measured parameters in Table 4 were different between WE₀

Fig. 6. Phase transition parameters for meibum from younger donor. X axis data are from mixtures listed in Table 1, where a value of 20 % represents 20 μL of the total amount of CE separated mixed with 80 μL of the total amount of WE separated. The molar ratio of CE/WE is listed in Table 1. A) Phase transition temperature, B) Lipid order at 33.4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the temperature of the tear film surface, C) Lipid order at 36 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the temperature of the meibomian glands, D) Maximum frequency, E) Change in the phase transition enthalpy, F) Change in the phase transition entropy.

Fig. 7. Standard curves used to convert CE/WE from total yielded to moles. A) Cholesteryl ester (CE). Wax ester (WE). X axis data are from mixtures listed in Table 1, where a value of 20 % represents 20 μL of the total amount of CE separated mixed with 80 μL of the total amount of WE separated. The molar ratio of CE/WE (Y axis) is listed in Table 1.

Table 4

Phase transition parameters for purified wax and cholesteryl esters from infrared spectroscopy.

Parameter	WE ₀	CE ₀	P, CE ₀ vs WE ₀	WE _y	CE _y	P, CE _y vs WE _y
Transition Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	32.3 ± 0.4	26.4 ± 0.8	< 0.0001	33.9 ± 0.3	37.1 ± 0.3	< 0.0001
Cooperativity (Hill coefficient)	5.8 ± 0.3	5.7 ± 0.9	> 0.5	8.9 ± 0.6	7.3 ± 0.4	0.037
Order 36.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (% trans)	38.0 ± 0.7	32.7 ± 2	0.02	43.2 ± 0.9	57.8 ± 1.2	< 0.0001
Order 33.4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (% trans)	44.5 ± 0.7	36.3 ± 2.5	0.005	54.2 ± 0.9	67.8 ± 1.2	< 0.0001
Δ enthalpy (kcal/mol)	135 ± 5	122 ± 5	> 0.5	186 ± 7	172 ± 8	> 0.5
Δ entropy (kcal.mol/degree)	0.44 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.02	> 0.5	0.61 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.03	> 0.5
Minimum Frequency (cm^{-1})	2849.54 ± 0.05	2849.2 ± 0.2	> 0.5	2848.84 ± 0.06	2848.67 ± 0.05	> 0.5
Maximum Frequency (cm^{-1})	2854.19 ± 0.08	2853.6 ± 0.2	0.012	2853.88 ± 0.09	2854.34 ± 0.06	0.0003

and WE_y and between CE₀ and CE_y. It is uncertain whether these differences are within the normal variation because infrared spectroscopic studies of purified WE and CE have never been performed. Future

infrared spectroscopic studies involving the relationships between purified WE and CE and age, race, sex and dry eye types are needed to bridge this gap in knowledge.

Table 5P values from Student's *t*-test for data from Figs. 3 and 4.

Phase transition parameter	Samples from (Fig. 4)		Samples from (Fig. 5)
	0 % CEo vs 20 % CEo (P)	100 % CEo vs 75 % CEo (P)	100 % CEy vs 75 % CEy (P)
Phase Transition Temperature	< 0.0001	0.012	0.002
Order at 33.4 °C	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Order at 36 °C	< 0.0001	0.0015	0.0002
Minimum Frequency	0.019	> 0.05	> 0.08
Maximum Frequency	> 0.05	0.006	0.048
Change in enthalpy (ΔH)	> 0.05	0.07	0.14
Change in entropy (ΔS)	> 0.05	0.06	0.19

CE = cholesteryl ester.

Table 6

Linear regression analysis for Figs. 4 and 5.

Phase transition parameter	Correlation coefficient (r)	P	Points Examined (%)
Cholesteryl and wax esters from the older donor			
Transition temperature	0.947	< 0.01	0 to 75
Order at 33.4 °C	0.815	< 0.05	0 to 75
Order at 36 °C	0.780	< 0.05	0 to 75
Minimum Frequency	0.911	< 0.01	20 to 100
Cholesteryl and wax esters from the younger donor			
Transition temperature	0.910	< 0.02	30 to 100
Order at 33.4 °C	0.765	< 0.05	30 to 100
Order at 36 °C	0.872	< 0.05	30 to 100
Maximum Frequency	0.991	< 0.01	40 to 100
Change in Enthalpy	0.866	< 0.02	0 to 75
Change in Entropy	0.884	< 0.01	0 to 75

4.3. Conformational changes when pure smectic CE is mixed with WE

X-ray crystallography of CE shows that at lower temperatures, CE is in the smectic phase (Fig. 8f), with their hydrocarbons, steroid nuclei, terminal methyl and ester carbonyl moieties adjacent to one another with their side chains interdigitated (Urata and Takaishi, 1997). An understanding of what happens to hydrocarbon chain conformation when pure smectic CE is mixed with WE provides insight into aim 3, 'why is WE and CE often present together and how does WE influence CE hydrocarbon chain conformation and visa-versa?'

4.3.1. Phase transition temperature and hydrocarbon chain order

More ordered WEy or less ordered WEo compared with CE, added to CE, decreases the phase transition temperature and hydrocarbon chain order of pure CE. This result is in agreement with model studies in which less ordered (compared with CE) stearyl palmitate or oleyl oleate, was added to cholesteryl behenate (Borchman et al., 2013; Hetman and Borchman, 2020).

4.3.2. Potential biological implications of changes in the phase transition temperature and hydrocarbon chain order

We theorize that hydrocarbon chain order results in increased cohesion between the lipid acyl chains and decreases the spreading of the lipids. Decreased spreading could impact the coating of lipid on the

surface of plants and on the exoskeleton of insects. More ordered lipid could decrease the spreading of the tear film lipid layer, which in turn may decrease tear film stability (Borchman, 2021; Georgiev et al., 2017). As a result, less ordered lipid, like WEo, could be necessary in the tear film lipid layer to disrupt the ordered packing of a hypothetical tear film lipid layer composed of only CE. Since the trends in the above results are similar for model and native CE, the complexity of the hydrocarbon chains are likely not to be a major influence on the order or phase transition temperature change when WE is added to pure CE.

4.3.3. Maximum and minimum frequencies of the phase transition

In terms of tear film lipids, it is somewhat inconsequential to discuss how the addition of WE to CE influences the the maximum and minimum frequencies of the phase transitions since these two parameters do not change in meibum from donors with or without meibomian gland dysfunction, $P = 0.09$ and 0.7 , respectively (Borchman, 2019). They do not change despite a large decrease in the CE/WE ratio of meibum from donors with MGD (Borchman et al., 2013; Hetman and Borchman, 2020). However, changes in the minimum and maximum frequencies of the phase transition when WE is added to CE could be important to WE/CE mixtures present in sebum, the cuticle of plants and the exoskeleton coating of insects.

Adding WE that is less ordered compared with CE decreased the maximum frequency of the phase transition. Thus, when the hydrocarbon chains of pure CE are fluid at higher temperatures, the addition of WE causes the packing of the resulting WE/CE mixture to arrange with more disordered hydrocarbon chains. No change in the maximum frequency was observed when adding less ordered (compared with cholesteryl behenate) oleyl oleate or stearyl palmitate was added to cholesteryl behenate (Borchman et al., 2013; Hetman and Borchman, 2020). This is evidence that the hydrocarbon chain branching or chain length caused the difference observed between the model and the native WE and CE moieties. Further evidence that the hydrocarbon chain composition influences the hydrocarbon chain conformation of native WE and CE comes from the observation that when WE is more ordered than CE, the maximum frequency increases, opposite of what occurs when WE is less ordered than CE. No model studies have been performed with more ordered WE added to less ordered CE, so no comparisons can be made. We conclude that how the conformation of pure smectic CE in the maximally disordered state changes with the addition of WE depends on whether the WE hydrocarbon chains are more or less ordered than CE and does not depend on merely on the ratio of CE to WE.

It is interesting that when the lipids are at low temperatures and maximally ordered, adding less ordered CEo to more ordered WEo causes the minimum frequency to decrease linearly, indicating that the mixture becomes even more ordered with the addition of CEo. This opposite trend was observed for the model system where very ordered cholesteryl behenate added to oleyl oleate caused the minimum frequency of the mixture to increase (order to decrease) (Hetman and Borchman, 2020). Since the trends for model and native systems are different in terms of the minimum frequency of the phase transition, the complexity of the native CE and WE acyl chains are likely to be a major influence on the minimum frequency of the phase transition when WE is added to pure CE.

4.4. Conformational changes when CE is mixed with pure lamellar WE

A more fluid CE compared with WE decreased the phase transition temperature, order and minimum frequency of WE. Adding more fluid CE compared with WE, to pure lamellar-packed WE had a profound effect on the phase transition parameters, whereas adding more ordered CE compared with WE, to purified WE had little effect. Based on our results, compared with a more ordered CE (relative to WE), a more fluid CE would be expected to have a more profound effect on the hydrocarbon chain conformation of tear film lipid, sebum, the cuticle of plants and the exoskeleton coating of insects composed only of WE.

Fig. 8. A) cholesteryl ester (CE), B) cholesteryl diester, C) wax ester (WE) and D) wax diester. CE and WE in a-d are drawn assuming a hydrocarbon chain length of 22 carbons (Janiak et al., 1979). E) Lamellar packing of pure WE from X-ray crystallography (Kreger and Schamhart, 2011; Simpson and Miwa, 1977; Weinbach et al., 1995), representative of 0 % CE in Figs. 3 and 4. (E, top) shows rhombic packing of the hydrocarbon chains. F) Smectic phase packing of CE (Weinbach et al., 1995) representative of 100 % CE in Figs. 3 and 4 from X-ray crystallography. G) Speculative packing of a WE, CE and phospholipid mixture on an aqueous surface (Wizert et al., 2017), representative of 20 to 75 % CE in Figs. 5 and 6.

4.4.1. Potential biological implications of the conformational changes when CE is mixed with pure lamellar WE

As a tear film lipid layer with more fluid meibum lipid hydrocarbon chains is expected to be more stable (Borchman, 2021; Georgiev et al., 2017), a more fluid CE (compared with WE) added to WE would likely be expected to stabilize the tear film lipid layer compared with a hypothetical tear film lipid layer composed of just WE alone.

4.5. Conformational changes when the concentration of CE changes in a mixture of WE and CE

Increasing amounts of less ordered CEo (compared with WEo) added to more ordered WEo caused the hydrocarbon chain order at 33.4 °C, phase transition temperature and minimum frequency to decrease linearly. This result is in agreement with model studies in which stearyl palmitate and oleyl oleate were added to cholesteryl behenate (Borchman et al., 2013; Hetman and Borchman, 2020). Since the trends in the results are similar for model and native CE, in this instance, differences in the complexity of the hydrocarbon chains are likely not to be a major influence on changes in the order or phase transition temperature when more ordered WE is added to less ordered CE. An opposite trend occurred when more ordered CEy (compared with WEy) was added in increments to less ordered WEy. Changes in CE content of WE/CE

mixtures undoubtedly changes the hydrocarbon chain conformation and packing of the mixture. The nature of the change depends on the conformation of the WE and CE.

4.5.1. Hydrocarbon chain branching, chain length and saturation of purified WE and CE

Although lipid hydrocarbon chain saturation is a major factor in 'setting' the general order of lipids, there is no evidence that hydrocarbon chain saturation changes with MGD. Raman (Oshima et al., 2009), NMR (Borchman and Ramasubramanian, 2019) and an infrared spectroscopic study (Borchman et al., 2020) show there is no difference in saturation for meibum from donors with MGD or without MGD. However, hydrocarbon chain saturation may play a role in ordering meibum and tear lipids from patients who had dry eye due to hematopoietic stem cell transplants (Borchman et al., 2020). To date, there is still no evidence that the hydrocarbon chain length for CE or WE is significantly different for meibum from donors with or without dry eye.

The average hydrocarbon chain branching of WE measured in this study was similar to that measured in other studies (Butovich et al., 2016; Nicolaidis et al., 1981). CEo had significantly less branched chains compared with WEo.

4.5.2. Potential biological implications of Hydrocarbon chain branching, chain length and saturation of purified WE and CE

Hydrocarbon chain branching would be expected to contribute to more disordered hydrocarbon chains and could account for why CE₀ was more disordered than CE₁, WE₀ and WE₁ (Urata and Takaishi, 1997). Hydrocarbon chain branching is unlikely to play a role in ordering meibum from donors with MGD as their meibum contained 14 % less straight chains compared with meibum from donors without MGD. This would disorder meibum not order it, as observed.

5. Conclusions and implications

- i WE could be separated from CE using MgO column chromatography.
- ii Changes in CE content of WE/CE mixtures undoubtedly modifies the hydrocarbon chain conformation and packing of the mixture. The nature of the effect depends on the conformation of the WE and CE. Differences in the complexity of the hydrocarbon chains are likely not to be a major influence on changes in the order or phase transition temperature when more ordered WE is added to less ordered CE.
- iii The major potential biological implications of our findings is that WE/CE mixtures could be advantageous in nature rather than WE or CE alone because a WE-CE mixture rather than CE alone, could be necessary in the tear film lipid layer to disrupt the ordered packing of pure CE resulting in better spreading of the lipids and thus to a more stable tear film. WE may also be a necessary component of sebum, the cuticle of plants and the exoskeleton coating of insects which would be expected to fluidize pure CE allowing the mixture to spread.

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Commercial relationships

None.

Availability of data and materials

All relevant raw data, may be made freely available to any researchers who wish to use them for non-commercial purposes, while preserving any necessary confidentiality and anonymity.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Written consents were obtained from the volunteers, and all protocols were in accordance with the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. Protocols and procedures for the current retrospective study were approved by the University of Louisville Institutional Review Board (# 11.0319, August 2016), and the Robley Rex Veterans Affairs Institutional Review Board.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization, Douglas Borchman; Data curation, Anthony Ewurum; Formal analysis, Anthony Ewurum, Ankem Akhila and Douglas Borchman; Funding acquisition, Douglas Borchman; Investigation, Anthony Ewurum, Ankem Akhila and Douglas Borchman; Methodology, Douglas Borchman; Project administration, Anthony Ewurum and Douglas Borchman; Resources, Georgi Georgiev and Douglas Borchman; Software, Douglas Borchman; Supervision, Douglas Borchman; Writing

– review & editing, Anthony Ewurum, Ankem Akhila and Georgi Georgiev.

Transparency document

The Transparency document associated with this article can be found in the online version.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors report no declarations of interest.

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